

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE INTERNATIONAL TOURIST MARKET IN THE GLOBAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. *This article examines the general conditions for the formation and development of the international tourism market in modern economic conditions. The article also shows the factors of the evolutionary development of the world economy and the role of the international tourism market in it.*

Keywords: *international tourism market, countries of the world, socio-economic changes, national economy, regions of the world.*

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the state of the processes of socio-economic development at the beginning of the century, the increasing interdependence of countries and regions of the world, the emergence and aggravation of new problems on a global scale under the influence of scientific and technological development, the Globalization processes are described as the acceleration of more intensive development. One of the most important features of the development of intensification processes at this stage is the interstate mixing of various factors of production and the unlimited movement of financial capital. As a result, globalization appears as a process that embraces all economic relations, and all its elements become increasingly compatible with each other, causing development.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the context of globalization, the government has established measures for the development of tourism in Uzbekistan, economic ties, various agreements and agreements with many countries are being implemented and expanded. At the same time, we believe that the following important work needs to be done in the field of international tourism.

1. Widespread use of marketing activities in international tourism and the desire to capture international markets;
2. Taking measures to disseminate and promote the tourism opportunities of Uzbekistan directly abroad through news agencies;
3. Training and education of specialists working in the field of tourism, creating all opportunities for them to provide quality services to tourists;
4. Constant participation in international tourism fairs;
5. Distribution of booklets, prospectuses and brochures about the types and quality of events necessary for implementation in the international tourism market of Uzbekistan;
6. Creation of joint ventures, companies and companies that can be active in the field of international tourism and expansion of their activities.

Further strengthening of competitive relations and other measures in tourist complexes of various small forms are of great importance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

As can be seen from Table 1, the arrival of foreign tourists to regions of the world in 1990 amounted to 435 million people. by 2023 it will reach 1 billion 400 million people.

Table 1

Influx of foreign tourists to regions of the world in 1990-2023. (million people)

Indicators	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2020	2021	2022	2023
Worldwide	435	527	674	809	951	1,189	1,235	1,323	1,400
Europe	261,5	304,5	386,6	453,2	489,4	607,7	619,7	671	713
Asia	55,9	82,1	110,4	154	205,5	279,2	302,9	324	343
America	92,8	108,9	128,2	133,3	150,2	192,6	200,9	208,7	217
Africa	14,8	18,7	26,2	34,8	50,4	53,5	58,2	62	67
Near East	9,6	12,7	22,4	33,7	54,7	53,3	53,6	58,1	64

The European region is the leader here, and the growth rate of tourist traffic is high. In the development of international tourism, it is also important to have tourism facilities that are attractive, relaxing and enjoyable. For example, in Europe there are theme parks that attract many tourists. One of these places is located in Tashkent, the capital of Uzbekistan, and it is associated with the activities of Disneyland and the Water Park. They have been operating since 1997 and are considered the most famous park not only in Uzbekistan, but also in Central Asia.

RESULTS

According to World Tourism Organization forecasts, the average annual growth rate of tourism until 2025 will be 4.1% in Europe, 7.8% in the Middle East, 7.5% in South Asia, 8% in East Asia and the Pacific. 0.2%. This figure was determined to be 15% for Uzbekistan and twice as high as in Asia. One of the main reasons for this is the territorial location of Uzbekistan within the countries of Central Asia, the availability of transport services for many countries and, finally, the fact that the number of visitors to Uzbekistan will increase only for the purpose of tourism.

In our opinion, its image is of great importance for the effectiveness of a tourism product in the tourism services market. Factors influencing the quality of household products may be the following: difficult environmental conditions, political conditions, linguistic, religious, ethnic conflicts among the population, low-level types of services, uninteresting architectural structures, etc. Summarizing the ideas presented above, we can see these factors at the level of economic, political, sociocultural, everyday and infrastructural factors (Table 2).

Table 2

Factors influencing product quality [5]

Political	Political situation in the country. Control is established by government agencies. Criminal proceedings.
Household	High level of cleanliness and hygiene in residential camp sites and similar places. Number of tourists in tourist centers. Nature, environment and cityscape beckon.
Economical	The relationship between the quality of services provided and prices.
Social-cultural	Socio-cultural characteristics and culture of the local community. The uniqueness of national art, crafts and traditions. Integrity of the local population.

Infrastructure	Compliance of infrastructure and utilities with international standards. Compliance of transport services with standards. Compliance of other types of facilities and services with international standards.
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CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The main characteristics of the foreign tourism market and its influence on determining the priorities of this sector can be determined by the composition of the flow of citizens coming to Uzbekistan. In order to determine this, additional information about the border crossing and the purpose of the trip is needed.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Message from the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev to the Supreme Assembly. // People's Word, December 30, 2020.
2. Dzhandyugazova E.A. Marketing of a tourist territory: textbook. A manual for university students studying in the field of education - Tourism / E.A. Dzhandzhugazova. - M.: Academy, 2008.
3. Kleiman A.A. On the new direction and strategy for the development of tourism business in the conditions of the economic crisis / A.A. Kleiman, O.A. Babanchikova // Bulletin of the National Academy of Tourism. 2015. N.1., Pp. 22-29.
4. Minaev, V.A. Regional tourism: forecasting and development planning in modern macroeconomic conditions / V.A. Minaev, N.A. Platonova, E.A. Tsischuk // Regional economics: theory and practice. - 2015. - N. 23 - Pp. 2-12.
5. Sevryukov I.Yu. Market of tourist services: current state and development trends // Economics: theory and practice. – 2016. – N. 4 – Pp. 43 – 48.
6. Morozov M.A. Entrepreneurship and competition in tourism: monograph / N.S. Morozova, M.A. Morozov. - M.: Russian New University, 2010.
7. www.ziynet.uz
8. www.stat.uz